

are some of the earliest rice strains. Because of their extreme earliness, they make a harvest possible in unirrigated drought-prone tracts of India and elsewhere.

Many CR666 lines that mature in 60 d have been identified. Some are intermediate in stature and grain size, and yield higher than the parents Sattari and Kalinga III although 10-20 d earlier than either. In progeny row trials during 1984 kharif, the strains were direct seeded and fertilized 1 wk after germination with 40 kg N/ha. Data on some of the promising lines are given in the table.

Subsequent bulk trials in 1985

Some agronomic characters of elite CR666 selections and their parents. Cuttack, India.

Culture or variety	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain size
CR666-36-69	85	60	3.3	Long bold
CR666-36-134	85	60	3.7	Long slender
CR666-36-162	80	57	2.9	Medium slender
CR666-36-173	85	60	4.0	Medium slender
CR666-36-322	90	58	3.8	Long slender
Sattari	70	70	2.3	Short bold
Kalinga III	125	80	3.8	Long slender
Rasi	85	115	4.2	Short bold

confirmed that the lines had a yield potential of 1.8 to 2.5 t/ha, comparable to the early parent Sattari. There has been an upgrading in height and grain

quality over Sattari, while reducing duration by more than 10 d. The productivity of these lines is more than 30 kg/ha daily. *ℓ*

DR92, a rice variety for low and medium altitudes

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DR92, a variety suitable for cultivation in puddled and upland conditions, has been released by Sikkim State Varietal Release Committee. A selection from the IET series, DR92 is medium tall, tillers profusely, and has good panicle exertion. Panicles are compact and

DR92 performance in Sikkim, India.

Variety	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Filled spikelets/panicle (no.)	Maturity (d)	Yield (t/ha)
DR92	90	14	146	130	5.5
Chirakey	119	9	94	145	1.7
Addey	115	8	89	148	2.0
Kanchi Addey	125	10	90	150	1.4

number of filled spikelets per panicle is high. The grains are medium sized and bold; kernels are light red and glutinous. DR92 is resistant to blast and stem

borer. It yields 40-60% more than predominant local varieties Chirakey, Addey, and Kanchi Addey (see table). *ℓ*

Three new high yielding rice varieties

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The Orissa State Seed Sub-committee in May 1985 released three promising CRRRI-developed varieties for general cultivation in Orissa. CR404-56-1 (Neela), CR407-19 (Sarasa), and CR190-103 (Udaya) have built-in resistance to major insect pests such as gall midge (GM), brown planthopper (BPH), and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH).

Neela is a selection from CR94-1512-6/ Pusa 2-21. It has semidwarf stature (65-70 cm), 90-d maturity (seed to seed), medium bold grains, and yields 3.0-3.5

t/ha. A derivative of PTB21 and PTB18 parents (CR94 series), Neela is resistant to GM, green leafhopper (GLH), and BPH. It is suitable for direct seeding in uplands in kharif and for transplanting in rabi where GM is a problem in the early crop.

Sarasa, a selection from CR94-1512-6/ Ratna, has semidwarf stature (80-85 cm), is weakly photoperiod sensitive, matures in 120-125 d in kharif (1 wk earlier in rabi at Cuttack), has long slender grains with head rice recovery of 50%, and yields 4-6 t/ha. A derivative of CR94, it is resistant to GM, BPH, and WBPH. Sarasa can withstand submergence for 7-10 d in the early vegetative stage. Sarasa is recommended for areas that are affected by early flooding followed by late season drought such as those in the Orissa coastal belt.

Udaya, a selection from CR129-118/CR57-49-2, is semidwarf (95-100 cm) and medium maturing (130 d). It has long bold grains and yields 5-6 t/ha. It is resistant to **BPH**, **WBPH**, **GM**, and **GLH**, and is tolerant of blast and tungro. Udaya is suitable for medium lands in kharif and rabi, particularly for areas where **BPH** is endemic. It has become popular in the second crop season in Cuttack and Puri Districts, where **BPH** infestation had caused farmers to switch to other crops. *ℓ*

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